

Viewers of Advertisements in Television and Cinema in the Shadow of Visuality

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Abstract—Despite the internet, which is one of the mass media that has become quite common in recent years, the relationship of Advertisement with Television and Cinema, which have always drawn attention of researchers as basic media and where visual use is in the foreground, have also become the subject of various studies. Based on the assumption that the known fundamental effects of advertisements on consumers are closely related to the creative process of advertisements as well as the nature and characteristics of the medium where they are used, these basic mass media (Television and Cinema) and the consumer motivations of the advertisements they broadcast have become a focus of study.

Given that the viewers of the mass media in question have shifted from a passive position to a more active one especially in recent years and approach contents of advertisements, as they do all contents, in a more critical and “pitiless” manner, it is possible to say that individuals make more use of advertisements than in the past and combine their individual goals with the goals of the advertisements. This study, which aims at finding out what the goals of these new individual advertisement use are, how they are shaped by the distinct characteristics of Television and Cinema, where visuality takes precedence as basic mass media, and what kind of places they occupy in the minds of consumers, has determined consumers’ motivations as: “Entertainment”, “Escapism”, “Play”, “Monitoring/Discovery”, “Opposite Sex” and “Aspirations and Role Models”.

This study intends to reveal the differences or similarities among the needs and hence the gratifications of viewers who consume advertisements on Television or at the Cinema, which are two basic media where visuality is prioritized.

Keywords—Cinema, Television, Viewers of Advertisements.

I. INTRODUCTION

AMONG tens of different definitions of advertisement, one is that “it is a marketing element that uses mass media”. Today, it is not quite possible for us to get rid of or avoid messages of advertisements; in short, we cannot think of life without advertisements. National and international companies do not leave any escape way to consumers by turning to new media (internet, cinema, product placement) as well as traditional advertising media (such as television, newspapers, magazines) in their effort to attain their goals. At this point, given the selectiveness of the target audience, what is important for advertisers is that marketing activities should be conducted without boring the target group no matter what the media used are.

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II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Television provides the advertiser with the opportunity to extend the message they wish to convey, the call they wish to make and the image they wish to create etc. in a stronger, effective and striking manner.

Besides all that is known about the television advertisements, what needs to be underlined in this study is also stated as avoidance of TV commercials in Suher and İspir’s article: There are different strategies about advertising avoidance [1]. Abernethy presents two strategies for advertising avoidance: Physical avoidance (leaving the room when advertisements begin) and mechanical avoidance (changing channel). Speck and Elliott offer three strategies for advertising avoidance. These are cognitive, behavioral, and mechanical strategies. Studies conducted on advertising avoidance focus mostly on television. Regarding TV commercials, viewers may not give their attention to advertisements by ignoring advertisements (cognitive strategy), may leave the room when advertisements begin (behavioral strategy) or change channels (mechanical strategy) [2].

Technological developments have made mechanical advertising avoidance more valid especially for television. Remote control devices and TIVO (devices that help record the relevant program by skipping advertisements in the program) facilitate the use of this strategy [3]. Television as a mass medium allows the avoidance in question and another mass medium, cinema, which does not, as will be mentioned later, leave much space for this avoidance.

Today, cinema advertising, which has gone beyond being a mere support medium for very many products and services in parallel to the rising number of viewers across the world, has become an important component of the media planning stage. Studies conducted in this regard indicate that viewers remember the advertisements they see in the cinema more than the advertisements they see on television. The most significant statistics in this framework appeared as a result of the study conducted by Lieberman Research in 2001 and Zenith Media in the year 2000. Lieberman emphasize that 85% of the cinema audience remember the advertisements they have seen on the screen later whereas Zenith points out that the rate of remembrance is 43% in the case of television [4]. Therefore, this corroborates Jean Luc Godard’s remark that “You raise your eyes at the cinema whereas you lower your eyes on television” [5]. When the matter is viewed from a global

perspective, it is seen that cinema advertising is used largely for image-making and product launching campaigns. Ubeyt Çağatay, general director of Artistik Hizmetler (Artistic Services) company, which engages in activities in the field of cinema advertising films, stated that according to a study conducted by The Screen Advertising World Association (SAWA), cinema is most frequently used by telecommunication, alcoholic beverages, communication, automotive, housing and finance sectors. Marketing Turkey magazine also pointed out that according to Cinema Advertising Activity Research conducted by a firm in Turkey, the ratio of those who remember on their own at least one of the advertisements shown in each series of advertisements at the cinema is 91% whereas when they are reminded of the advertisements, this ratio rises to as high as 98% [6]. Thus, it can be said that advertisements shown at the cinema are among the best remembered in comparison to those shown on television, on the radio, and in other media. There are various reasons why cinema advertising, which can be defined as a type of advertising that has high visual quality and appeals to the audience directly, is preferred by advertisers. Used as an advertising medium for these reasons, cinema may exhibit similarities to television due to its visual nature but it is defined as a medium that will not replace cinema but complement it [7]. It should be noted that cinema is preferred as an advertising medium by virtue of its “Viewer Profile, Captive Viewer, Interactive Marketing Possibilities, General Atmosphere, Measurable Medium” [8].

In the widest sense, advertisements are oriented towards cognitive and emotional needs and, according to Mohan; it is possible to detect advertisements behind and in front of all the needs of individuals concerning life [9]. Insights of viewers, which need to be taken into consideration in all strategic creative decisions in the production of advertisements, consist of various needs. This means that advertisements will be appreciated by the viewers in accordance with their needs. Advertisements and media, which are almost everywhere at all times in the satisfaction of various needs of individuals due in part to the effect of sectoral and technological developments, may assume different functions. Individuals’ motivational orientation based on needs and their desire for gratification also means that they undertake a participatory role in the process of advertisement communication [10]. Individuals’ orientation towards their own interests, search for these interests and indifference, apathy and rejection to those other than their interests and needs shape the levels of use and gratification of advertisement messages in different media [11].

Indeed, in this new age, individuals vis-a-vis advertisements are defined as “experienced viewers” in a society which is composed of advertisement consumers who exhibit behaviors such as avoiding advertisements, selective perception and partial processing on the basis of their needs, beliefs and attitudes [12]. Recent social and psychological studies indicate that advertisement communication is a dynamic and interactional process and that in this process viewers are not passive recipients of messages but rather individuals who take

whichever of these messages they wish to take [13]. Unlike the traditional approach, the novel one reveals that advertisements do not make viewers do something; instead, viewers benefit from and “use” advertisements as they like and to the extent they wish in order to determine their preferences [14]. This situation indicates that it is the recipient of the message rather than the sender that is at the helm of the process. For individuals who, apart from basic physiological and informational marketing/non marketing needs, act on the basis of needs such as socialization, sexuality, dependence, guidance, achievement, superiority, autonomy, avoidance, feeling secure, aesthetics and satisfying their curiosity [15], advertisements appear as vital products that are utilized in marketing use and serve to meet both cognitive and emotional needs.

III. METHODOLOGY

The type of the study is an exploratory one. The purpose in exploratory studies, which contain efforts to determine causes and effects of a phenomenon without a specific expectation, and which aim to find out what meanings individuals who participate in a study attach to their behaviors, what they are interested in and what they deem important, is to seek answers to the questions of “why” and “how” [16]. In this context, they are considered to be quite useful in determining motivations. Since it was not possible to reach all the individuals who are advertising viewers in the research population, a sample representing the population was selected impartially. The “simple random sampling” method was used in the selection of the sample. In the simple random sampling method, impartial selection is performed taking into consideration the possibility that each unit in the population is equal and independent when being selected for the sample [17], so each subject in the population enjoys equal chances to be included in the sample and can readily represent the population [18]. Thus, it was ensured that the 400 individuals who were included in the sample of the study were impartially selected and represented differences adequately and the study was conducted in different regions within the borders of the province of Konya.

The present study, which involved 400 male and female participants who live in Konya and come from different occupational statuses, different age groups and different educational levels, focuses on advertisements on Television and at the Cinema, where visual use is prioritized, and motivations are assessed separately.

A scale consisting of 66 items/statements was designed and administered in order to determine what advertisements participants of the study used in what media to satisfy what needs. The positions of the participants were measured within the range of 5 “I totally agree” and 1 “I totally disagree” in a likert type ordering through emotional and cognitive motivations that were determined in the uses and gratifications studies aimed at advertisements and statements prepared by the help of findings aimed at perceptions of media. 4 of the items in the survey were related to the demographic features of the participants. Exploratory Factor Analysis was used to

analyze the data. To be able to see the overall properties of the participants, descriptive statistics, frequencies tables and Reliability Analysis were used.

IV. FINDINGS AND COMMENTS

In the study, 66 descriptive statements for each medium (2 different media) were evaluated separately using factor analysis. Below are analyses for each of the media.

A. Television

The first table (Table I) includes motivations for viewing the medium of television. Minimum loading value was taken to be .25, whereas the eigenvalue was defined to be higher than one. According to this, 5 factors accounting for 46% of the total variance were obtained. Total reliability of the 66 statements was .955.

The first of the factors obtained from the factor analysis reveals that television advertisements fulfill the function of "Environmental Scanning" for viewers. This factor alone accounts for 11.43% of the variance and its eigenvalue is 7.54 while its reliability (Cronbach's Alpha) is .905. According to the statements in the factors, television advertisements fulfill the functions of "Support of attitudes and values", "Identifying Opposite sex", "Aspirations and role models", "Coaching and Proficiency" "Exploration and Surveillance", and "Associating" for the viewers.

The second factor, which is defined as "Psychosocial Uses/Relationships", consists of concepts such as "Peer Relationships", "Family Relationships", "Ego Enhancement", "Education", "Sharing" Play", and "Entertainment". This factor accounts for 9.57% of the variance and its eigenvalue is 6.31, while its reliability (Cronbach's Alpha) is .891.

The third factor, which involves the concepts of "Quality Assurance / Satisfaction / Dispelling of Doubts" and "Representative Consumption", is defined as "Consumption Satisfaction". This factor accounts for 9.56% of the total variance and its eigenvalue is 6.31. Its reliability, on the other hand (Cronbach's Alpha), is .897.

The fourth factor is called "Marketing Information". This factor, which consists of concepts such as "Acquisition of Knowledge", "Selection", and "Preference through Comparison", reveals the use of television advertisements for

marketing purposes. This factor accounts for 8.25% of the total variance. Its eigenvalue is 5.44, and reliability is .876. The fifth factor explaining the reasons for viewing television advertisements contains the concepts of "Structuring Time, Diversion, and Escapism". This factor is called "Structuring Time and Entertainment". It is understood that television advertisements are seen as an alternative way of spending free time and as an activity allowing escape from life. This factor accounts for 7.19% of the total variance. Its eigenvalue is 4.78 and reliability is .864.

According to the findings of Descriptive Statistics regarding television, the statements that associate most frequently and have the highest mean values are "I find them useful for discovering the latest products" (M=4.01, Sd.=1.20); "They enable me to perceive the competition among products" (M=3.96, Sd.=1.26); "Most of the time, the story of the advertisement, photographs, music, visuals and performers etc. rather than the brands seem more interesting" (M=3.93, Sd.=1.35); and "It is easier for me to make decisions during shopping as I remember the products that are advertised" (M=3.91, Sd.=1.29). In this context, television as a medium of advertising is seen as enabling consumers to encounter innovations, allowing emergence of new consumer needs/ideas, and providing ease for making preferences. Despite all other technological advancements, television seems to maintain its role as the key medium that introduces consumers to innovations. It is understood that television advertisements, by virtue of production features and the formats used, not only fulfill the function of marketing use but also the function of a television program with their stories and music. Its focus on presentation rather than the use of the product is considered to be a characteristic of the medium. The motivation statements with the lowest mean values are "I enjoy listening to stories" (M=2.41, Sd.=1.46), "Advertisements provide pleasure like playing games" (M=2.44, Sd.=1.47), and "Advertisements remove monotony and provide an opportunity to see a colorful and pleasant world" (M=2.72, Sd.= 1.47). In other words, participants stated that they did not agree with these statements. We can say that television is regarded as part of the routine of life rather than as a medium of play/pleasure.

TABLE I
 MOTIVATIONS FOR TELEVISION ADVERTISEMENTS

Environmental Scanning	1	2	3	4	5
They offer ideas about what is valuable and important in life	.688				
They can provide a point of view regarding what is good and bad and what is useful and useless in life	.633				
I may have an opportunity to understand and know the opposite sex	.655				
There are times when I compare patterns of behavior in advertisements with mine	.625				
There are times when I aspire to the lifestyles in advertisements	.613				
I find things related to my own values of life	.610				
I encounter things that provide inspiration for my life	.594				
It is possible to learn what is happening in the world from advertisements	.592				
Being informed of advertisements enables me to understand what is going on	.577				
I relate what I see in advertisements to my life	.551				
Advertisements offer an opportunity to see ideal women and men (body, clothing, behavior etc.)	.540				
I learn certain new things from advertisements which I did not know previously	.536				
They enable me to discover different things beyond the products	.529				
I have an opportunity to see other lives	.487				
I get annoyed when I do not understand advertisements	.456				

Psycho-social Uses / Relationships	1	2	3	4	5
Advertisements can be a source of jokes among my friends		.728			
Advertisements can be a source of jokes among family members		.672			
Advertisements can be a subject of conversation among my friends		.623			
I share my views and criticisms about advertisements		.591			
Advertisements can be a subject of conversation and a part of the agenda within the family		.585			
It is pleasurable to criticize advertisements		.573			
Advertisements can be instructive on certain vital topics (Health, Traffic, Social Life etc.)		.553			
Advertisements can be a source of jokes among us		.533			
Being able to understand covert meanings in advertisements enable me to feel good		.523			
Most of the time, the story of the advertisement, photographs, music, visuals and performers etc. rather than the brands seem more interesting		.517			
Sometimes, the beauty or good-looks of the people in advertisements appeal to me more than the product		.506			
They are informative about issues such as decoration, fashion etc. besides information about the product		.471			
I can learn new trends in many fields and the latest fashion through advertisements		.437			
They provide me with ideas about changes to my outer appearance (hair color, weight, clothing etc.)		.427			
I like seeing things related to my life in advertisements (events, locations, etc.)		.403			
They help kill time		.399			
Advertisements are like having a break to take care of other things (making a phone call with someone, making tea etc.)		.282			
Consumption Satisfaction	1	2	3	4	5
Seeing the advertisement of a brand in this medium provides me with confidence in this brand			.738		
They help dispel my doubts about a product			.689		
I find a brand being advertised stronger than others			.682		
I find the image and identity of the brand being advertised stronger than its competitors			.681		
If I do not see advertisements of a brand in this medium, I have negative views about that brand			.681		
Presence of advertisements of a product is in a way a quality assurance			.651		
Advertisements help reduce risks in my shopping			.639		
Advertisements about a product that I use make me feel good			.638		
I think that products that are advertised are good quality and prestigious			.628		
I think that products that are advertised are good quality and prestigious			.628		
I like being a consumer of a product being advertised in this medium			.537		
I experience being the user of a product through advertisements			.532		
Even if I do (or can) not buy that product, I have sense of what it would be like to have it			.519		
I have confidence in products that are advertised and feel more comfortable during shopping			.510		
Marketing Information	1	2	3	4	5
They help me learn things that I do not know about the product				.697	
They help me see the range of products and thus make comparisons				.691	
They help me better appreciate the uses of the product				.657	
I find them useful in that they help me discover the latest products				.629	
I encounter a wider range of alternatives and this gives me freedom as a consumer				.627	
They help me perceive competition among products				.619	
I make faster decisions during shopping because I remember the products that are advertised				.569	
Advertisements facilitate the process of making decisions before I buy				.565	
I find them useful in that I can learn about discounts and promotions offered by specific brands				.542	
They help reinforce my knowledge about a product				.537	
I can learn about technical properties of a product				.450	
Structuring Time and Entertainment	1	2	3	4	5
I can get a diversion through advertisements					.710
They help me escape when I am bored					.687
Advertisements offer pleasure just like playing games					.658
Advertisements remove monotony and provide an opportunity to see a more colorful and pleasant world					.654
Advertisements are usually more exciting and delightful than their contents (programs, news etc.)					.643
I derive pleasure from them just as I do from listening to stories					.638
They help me pass time when I am bored					.557
I watch them when I have nothing more important					.525
I find them fun and interesting					.505
Advertisements help me take a break to think and talk about things that I read and watch (series, news, films)					.470
Eigenvalue	7.54	6.31	6.31	5.44	4.74
% of Variance	11.43	9.57	9.56	8.25	7.19
Cronbach's Alpha	.905	.891	.897	.876	.864

B. Cinema

The second table (Table II) includes motivations for viewing the medium of cinema. Minimum loading value was taken to be .25, whereas the eigenvalue was defined to be higher than one. According to this, 5 factors accounting for 58% of the total variance were obtained. Total reliability of the 66 statements was .974.

The first of the factors obtained from the Factor Analysis, reveals that cinema commercials fulfill the function of

“Environmental Scanning and Relationships” in terms of audience. This factor alone accounts for 20.99% of the variance and its eigenvalue is 13.85 while its reliability (Cronbach’s Alpha) stands at .962. According to the statements in the factor, cinema advertising fulfils the functions of “Support of attitudes and values”, “Identifying Opposite sex”, “Aspirations and role models, “Exploration and Surveillance” and “Associating” for the audience.

The second factor is called “Marketing Information”. Involving the concepts of “Information”, “Selection,

Preference”, this factor leads one, regarding the marketing aspect of cinema advertising, to rethink the judgment that “Cinema advertising aims at creating images”, which is claimed to come to the foreground in some studies. This factor accounts for 16.22% of the total variance. Its eigenvalue is 10.70 and its reliability stands at .941.

The third factor, which is called “Entertainment”, involves concepts such as “Play”, ”Entertainment”, “Escapism” and Diversion”. This factor accounts for 12.65% of the variance; its eigenvalue is 8.35 and its reliability (Cronbach’s Alpha) is .917.

The fourth factor is called “Added Value” because it includes all the motivations under this heading. This factor accounts for 4.64% of the total variance and its eigenvalue is 3.306 while its reliability stands (Cronbach’s Alpha) at .861.

The fifth factor explaining why cinema advertisements are watched involves the concepts of “Added Value” and “Ego Enhancement”. This factor is called “Identifying with the Product”. It accounts for 3.59% of the total variance. Its eigenvalue is 2.37 and reliability is .359.

According to the findings of Descriptive Statistics regarding cinema, the statements that most go together and have the highest mean values are “Most of the time, the story of the advertisement, photographs, music, visuals and performers etc. rather than the brands seem more interesting” (M=2.63,

Sd.=1.59); “Advertisements about a product that I use make me feel good” (M=2.57, Sd.=3.04); “Advertisements can be a subject of conversation among my friends” (M=2.55, Sd.=1.53); “Advertisements can be instructive on certain vital topics (Health, Traffic, Social Life etc.)” (M=2.54, Sd.=1.67). These results indicate that like television, cinema is a medium which is dominated by visuality, has a story and where some spiritual satisfactions presented by advertising production rather than the material benefits of products are prioritized. However, it should also be emphasized that the judgment that cinema advertisements bring evocations merely about image creation has not been much corroborated by the study sample and that it needs to be reconsidered.

The motivation statements with the lowest means are “I derive pleasure from them just as I do from listening to stories” (M=1.93, Sd.=1.30), “Advertisements offer pleasure just like playing games” (M=1.95, Sd.=1.34), “They help reinforce my knowledge about a product” (M=2.00, Sd.=1.27) and “Advertisements remove monotony and provide an opportunity to see a more colorful and pleasant world” (M=2.01, Sd.=1.30). In other words, individuals do not agree with these judgments. We can say that as far as cinema is concerned, the participants, like on television, regard advertisements as part of the daily routine of life and a means of self-fulfillment rather than a medium of play.

TABLE II
 MOTIVATIONS FOR CINEMA ADVERTISEMENTS

	1	2	3	4	5
Environmental Scanning and Relationships					
Advertisements can be a source of jokes among family members	.761				
Advertisements can be a subject of conversation and a part of the agenda within the family	.730				
I relate what I see in advertisements to my life	.727				
I learn certain new things from advertisements which I did not know previously	.716				
I may have an opportunity to understand and know opposite sex	.694				
They offer ideas about what is valuable and important in life	.680				
Advertisements can be a source of jokes among my friends	.678				
Advertisements offer an opportunity to see ideal women and men (body, clothing, behavior etc.)	.677				
I have an opportunity to see other lives	.663				
I encounter things that provide inspiration for my life	.662				
Advertisements can be a subject of conversation among my friends	.659				
It is possible to learn what is happening in the world from advertisements	.659				
I find things related to my own values of life	.656				
I can learn new trends in many fields and the latest fashion through advertisements	.641				
Advertisements can be instructive on certain vital topics (Health, Traffic, Social Life etc.)	.641				
They are informative about issues such as decoration, fashion etc. besides information about the product	.637				
I like seeing things related to my life in advertisements (events, locations, remarks etc.)	.625				
Being informed of advertisements enables me to understand what is going on	.625				
Being able to understand covert meanings in advertisements enable me to feel good	.610				
They enable me to discover different things beyond the products	.601				
They provide me with ideas about changes to my outer appearance (hair color, weight, clothing etc.)	.599				
There are times when I aspire to the lifestyles in advertisements	.562				
It is pleasurable to criticize advertisements	.561				
I get annoyed when I do not understand advertisements	.509				
Marketing Information					
They help me see the range of products and thus make comparisons		.768			
They help reinforce my knowledge about a product		.767			
I find them useful in that they help me discover the latest products		.742			
They help me better appreciate the uses of the product		.742			
They help me learn things that I do not know about the product		.741			
They help me perceive competition among products		.711			
I encounter a wider range of alternatives and this gives me freedom as a consumer		.710			
I find them useful in that I can learn about discounts and promotions offered by specific brands		.687			
I have confidence in products that are advertised and feel more comfortable during shopping		.677			
I make faster decisions during shopping because I remember the products that are advertised		.675			
Advertisements facilitate the process of making decisions before I buy		.648			
I can learn about technical properties of a product		.625			
Advertisements help reduce risks in my shopping		.615			

Entertainment	1	2	3	4	5
Advertisements offer pleasure just like playing games			.748		
Advertisements remove monotony and provide an opportunity to see a more colorful and pleasant world			.728		
I derive pleasure from them just as I do from listening to stories			.716		
I can get a diversion through advertisements			.711		
They help me escape when I am bored			.671		
Advertisements are usually more exciting and delightful than their contents (programs, news etc.)			.657		
They help me pass time when I am bored			.594		
I watch them when I have nothing more important			.558		
Advertisements help me take a break to think and talk about things that I read and watch (series, news, films)			.524		
I find them fun and interesting			.510		
Added Value	1	2	3	4	5
I find the image and identity of the brand being advertised stronger than its competitors				.623	
I find a brand being advertised stronger than others				.579	
I think that products that are advertised are good quality and prestigious				.573	
Advertisements can be a source of jokes among us				.567	
They help kill time				.485	
Advertisements are like having a break to take care of other things (making a phone call with someone, making tea etc.)				.478	
Identification with the product	1	2	3	4	5
Advertisements about a product that I use make me feel good					.840
I share my views and criticisms about advertisements					.826
Eigenvalue	13.85	10.70	8.35	3.06	2.37
% of Variance	20.99	16.22	12.65	4.64	3.59
Cronbach's Alpha	.962	.941	.917	.861	.859

IV. CONCLUSION

The factors obtained from the study reveal what needs are satisfied by viewing advertisements on television and at the cinema. It can be said that besides these two media, which can be considered to be dominated by visuality, in other visuality-dominated media (newspapers, magazines, and outdoors etc.) too, other elements of advertising (like writing) come into play especially due to the stability of the image. However, the audiences of television and cinema, which are media where images are turned into stories within the framework of a scenario, are active and selective about advertisements and apart from that they use these advertisements and their messages in order to meet their different needs in contrast to their original purpose. This is so much so that it is understood from the study that television advertisements, by virtue of their making and the formats used, fulfill not only the marketing use function but also a television program function with their stories and music. On the other hand, it can also be concluded that cinema advertisements are found interesting by viewers with their photographs, music and actors and actresses, that when viewers encounter the product they use, they make an association and feel better, that advertisements are among the daily conversation topics and that they can play an informative part on vital issues.

Although audiences sometimes tend to avoid television advertisements there does not seem to exist such an alternative for cinema audiences. Moreover, cinema possesses better facilities, by virtue of its overall atmosphere, in creating the situation where the source of the advertisement wants to meet the audience. In fact, television and cinema audiences do more with advertisements than what the advertisers have intended for and planned and here the power of the image plays a major part.

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